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Evaluation of Base4NFDI

Inception report

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Table of Contents

1	Context and goals of the evaluation and the inception report	1
2	Impact model	2
3	Evaluation concept	5
3.1	Evaluation questions and concept	5
3.2	Operationalisation of the evaluation approach	6
4	Work plan	8
4.1	WP 1: Inception report	8
4.2	WP 2: Interview programme 1	9
4.3	WP 3: Online surveys	10
4.3.1	Survey with consortia members	11
4.3.2	Survey with the developer teams	12
4.4	WP 4: Interview deep-dives & focus groups	12
4.5	WP 5: Workshops with Base4NFDI members	13
4.6	WP 6: Data triangulation and evaluation report	14
5	Time plan	16
	Appendix A Interview guide	17
	Appendix B Survey questionnaires	22

Tables

Table 1	Three levels of the evaluation with key questions	5
Table 2	Inception phase: timeline of remaining steps	9
Table 3	Interview topics covered per target group	10
Table 4	Interview guide: question blocks	17

Figures

Figure 1	Goals of the evaluation	2
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Figure 2	Impact model	4
Figure 3	Methodological operationalisation	7
Figure 4	Time plan for the evaluation	16

1 Context and goals of the evaluation and the inception report

Base4NFDI is a joint initiative of all consortia of German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). At its core, Base4NFDI operates under the following mission statement:¹

“Base4NFDI serves as a framework to support the development of a basic service portfolio to meet the needs of the scientific community. Base4NFDI supports the NFDI Sections in identifying basic service candidates, involving relevant stakeholders and existing services, and ensuring their suitability and adoption. It accompanies the development and consolidation of the services in three successive development phases, at the same time leveraging synergies between the NFDI consortia. With a long-term perspective, Base4NFDI contributes to the evolution and innovation of the service landscape.”

To achieve this mission, Base4NFDI pursues the following key objectives:

- Providing a fair, transparent and coherent framework for the NFDI community to propose, develop and implement potential basic service candidates
- Encourage community-driven co-design of basic services and support the active participation of the entire NFDI community in the identification, development, and implementation of basic services
- Delivering a portfolio of basic services which can be used by potentially all NFDI-consortia and the wider NFDI-community and contribute to a federated NFDI data infrastructure which is embedded in international (infra-)structures (e.g. European Open Science Cloud (EOSC))

To evaluate Base4NFDI effectively, it is crucial to consider the current state of the project. Since its inception in 2023, three basic services have progressed to the second development phase (integration), while five additional services remain in the first stage (initialisation). Notably, none have yet advanced to the final ramping-up phase. In addition, the evaluation must account for the high level of heterogeneity among stakeholders, who represent a wide range of research disciplines. This complexity is further compounded by the staggered launch of NFDI consortia across three distinct funding periods between 2020 and 2023. Whilst some consortia are already fully operational, others remain in their early stages of development. Finally, it is important to recognise that Base4NFDI itself is still in its formative phase, with processes being newly established and continuously refined.

Besides the evaluation of Base4NFDI, several other evaluations and studies are currently being carried out in the NFDI environment: The structural evaluation of the NFDI is conducted by the German Science and Humanities Council (Wissenschaftsrat, WR). Additionally, the German Research Foundation (DFG) assesses the work of the individual consortia. Complementing these efforts, the DZHW carries out accompanying research for Base4NFDI, focusing on a systematic impact assessment.

Figure 1 portrays the goals of the evaluation. Overall, the evaluation seeks to evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness of the project structure of Base4NFDI and its established processes. Furthermore, the evaluation examines the relevance of the developed basic services for the consortia members in the NFDI community.

The present Inception Report aims to define the key questions of the evaluation, specify the methodology to be used, and finalise the individual data collection steps in consultation with the client. The Inception Report forms the foundation for all subsequent stages of the

¹ Base4NFDI: Mission statement. Online: <https://base4nfdi.de/about/mission-statement> [last accessed: 23.01.2025].

evaluation. The next chapter introduces the impact model, which outlines the mechanisms of action of Base4NFDI. The evaluation concept is briefly presented in Chapter 3, followed by a detailed work programme in Chapter 4. Finally, the timeline for the evaluation is presented in Chapter 5.

Figure 1 Goals of the evaluation

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2 Impact model

Figure 2 illustrates our understanding of the project's impact logic, which forms the foundation of our evaluation approach. The impact model is structured into inputs (resources and structures), processes, outputs (direct results of inputs and processes), outcomes (effects on the target audience), and impacts (long-term systemic effects). At the **input** level, key elements include the financial resources provided by the DFG to fund Base4NFDI, the technical infrastructure supplied by NFDI consortia/members for service development, and the work undertaken by the sections and especially the development teams and the Base4NFDI team. The **processes** encompass identifying, discussing and proposing basic services for development as well as processes for assessing and voting and such proposals. The technical development processes are accompanied by activities to promote the visibility and deployment of basic services in the consortia (e.g. outreach, training, knowledge sharing). Furthermore, overarching strategic and management processes support the project. At the **output** level, the impact model aims for adequate collaborative processes for identifying, developing and deploying basic services while ensuring adequate process and resource management and conducting adequate training and communication activities. The **outcomes** for the NFDI community include a trusted participatory framework for developing basic services which serves as a basis that the developed services are deployed and used in the (wider) NFDI community and integrated into international research data frameworks such as EOOSC. Further outcomes include optimised research data infrastructures and (cross-disciplinary) research collaborations. As a long-term systemic **impact**, the goal is to establish

sustainable research data management aligned with the FAIR principles, thereby enhancing research competitiveness and fostering innovation. Given the current developmental stage of the services, the **evaluation primarily focuses on the processes and outputs** (highlighted in red).

Figure 2 Impact model

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3 Evaluation concept

3.1 Evaluation questions and concept

The key questions for evaluating Base4NFDI can be clustered into **three different levels** (see Table 1). **Level 1** addresses the **internal structure** of Base4NFDI and examines the roles of project members, the work organisation and the collaboration within the Base4NFDI team (meaning TAs and SERs). Here, the aim is to assess how well the project structure works, whether the objectives defined in the project proposal are being achieved and whether the available resources are being used efficiently.

Level 2 aims at the decision and **development process** for basic services and can be sub-grouped into:

- the process for discussing, identifying and proposing basic service candidates (in the consortia/sections/working groups)
- the decision-making processes for basic service candidates (decisions in the TEC, the consortia assembly as well as in the consortia)
- the processes for developing and deploying basic services (three stage development process, activities for promoting and deploying basic services)

Finally, the **relevance** of the developed basic services for the NFDI community and **strategic aspects** of Base4NFDI are addressed in **level 3**.

Several **interlinkages between the levels** exist. For instance, actors which are involved in level 2 are supported by the Base4NFDI team, stakeholders which are the target group of level 3 (consortia members) might also be involved in processes of level 2.

Table 1 Three levels of the evaluation with key questions

Level 1	Key questions
Level 1: Internal structure, roles & areas of responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are the task areas defined in the proposal adequately staffed and covered? (Relevance) • Are all the responsibilities mentioned in the proposal adequately addressed? (Effectiveness) • Do internal communication and organisational workflows function efficiently? (Efficiency) • Do the job profiles align with the project's requirements, and are tasks clearly communicated? (Efficiency) • Are there tasks that cannot be completed due to a lack of resources? (Efficiency) • Are all necessary resources and information provided to the relevant stakeholders? (Efficiency)
Level 2: Basic services development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do various external stakeholders assess cooperation with Base4NFDI, particularly with the service stewards and section liaison officers? (Relevance) • Are the reasons for adjustments, such as costs or new/unanticipated tasks, comprehensible? (Effectiveness) • Are the decision-making processes and the subsequent allocation of funds, transparent and understandable for stakeholders? (Efficiency) • Is the proposal submission process transparent and fair? (Coherence) • Are the criteria for evaluating incoming proposals clearly communicated? (Coherence) • Does the technical expertise within the TEC (Technical Expert Committee) complement each other in evaluating proposals? (Coherence)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the process ensure that the "common needs" outlined in the proposal are identified and addressed through basic services? (Effectiveness) • Are NFDI structures sufficiently involved? (Effectiveness) • Is the development process regularly analysed and improved? (Efficiency)
Level 3: Relevance of the project for the NFDI community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is Base4NFDI achieving the objectives set at the time of evaluation, in line with the work programme and stakeholder expectations? (Relevance) • Has the work programme been adapted to meet any emerging needs? (Effectiveness) • Does the process ensure that the basic services are state-of-the-art and best suited to requirements, while also guaranteeing integration into international initiatives? (Effectiveness, Coherence)

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Overall, Base4NFDI has **many different groups of actors and stakeholders** which are relevant for multiple levels of the evaluation. These include the NFDI consortia and sections, the basic service developer teams, the TEC and the Base4NFDI team. In addition, several strategic bodies are relevant for the project, e.g. the NFDI Scientific Senate, the International Advisory Board (IAB), the Rat für Informationsinfrastrukturen (RfII) and the Wissenschaftsrat.

In order to adequately and comprehensively consider these different perspectives and to examine them in more depth at appropriate points, we believe that an **evaluation of a formative character** is necessary, which **sequentially examines and compares the perspectives of process participants and stakeholders** to identify optimisation potentials. To this end, the **internal perspectives of the project participants** who are directly involved in the Base4NFDI (Base4NFDI Team, TEC, development teams) are contrasted with the "**external perspectives**" of those stakeholders who identify potential basic service candidates (sections) and those who are meant to use it (members of the NFDI consortia) or strategically advise the project (e.g. IAB, Scientific Senate of the NFDI).

By comparing these perspectives, strengths, divergences and needs for action can be systematically identified for the project. Based on this comparison, an **in-depth analysis** will be carried out to shed light on existing differences in more detail and to identify possible solutions. The insights gained from the sequential survey of views will then be brought together and finally reflected on and discussed with the Base4NFDI team. Based on this, recommendations for action for the further development of the Base4NFDI framework are developed.

3.2 Operationalisation of the evaluation approach

We propose a **mix of qualitative and quantitative methods** to operationalise the key questions of the evaluation appropriately. Figure 3 highlights our methodological approach for the evolution which we briefly explain below.

Figure 3 Methodological operationalisation

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1. Concept phase (WP 1)

The concept phase builds the basis of the evaluation and prepares all further evaluation steps. Therefore, we conduct comprehensive **document analysis** and four scoping interviews during the inception phase to develop a profound understanding of the strategic goals of Base4NFDI and the project itself to refine the evaluation questions and to concretise further data collection steps.

2. Exploratory data collection phase (WP 2 & 3)

To capture the **internal and external perspectives** adequately, we conduct:

- a guideline-based, **exploratory interview programme** (interview programme 1) to **qualitatively** capture the internal perspectives of the Base4NFDI team, the TEC, the developer teams as well as the external views of section and consortia speaker and strategic governance bodies such as the IAB, the Scientific Council or the Rfll. In total, we are planning **32 interviews** as part of the first interview programme.
 - **two online surveys** to **quantitatively** capture the external views of consortia members and the internal perspectives of all members of the developer teams
- ### 3. Synthesis, identification of critical points, deep dives: interviews, focus groups, workshops (WP 4 & 5)

The (interim) results of the first interview programme and the online surveys will be compared and assessed in a next step. Based on this, **needs for more in-depth interviews (interview programme 2)** will be identified in selected areas of the project in which we identified discrepancies, ambiguities or contradictions that require closer investigation. In total, we are planning about **15 interviews** as part of the second interview programme. In addition to the interview deep dives, we plan to conduct **two focus groups** with different stakeholders or process participants of Base4NFDI, as they promote the exchange between the participants and directly contrast different perspectives. This makes it possible to identify common

challenges and make synergy potentials visible that may not be recognizable in individual interviews.

The results of the previous data collection steps will then be further deepened and validated in **two workshops with the Base4NFDI team**. From our point of view, there are two workshops that cover the respective governance areas of the project:

- Workshop 1 with members from TA 1 and TA 2 and selected Service Stewards
- Workshop 2 with members from TA 3 and TA 4 and selected Service Stewards

Both workshops will cover all three levels of the evaluation since they are closely intertwined. While Workshop 1 focuses slightly more on level 2 (service development), Workshop 2 focuses slightly more on level 3 (relevance and strategy) of the evaluation. As the Service Stewards play a crucial role across all three evaluation levels, we plan to invite selected Service Stewards to participate in the workshops, with some attending Workshop 1 and others Workshop 2

4. Reporting

Finally, the results will be consolidated in the context of a comprehensive data triangulation. In addition, recommendations for action for the further development of the Base4NFDI framework will be formulated on the basis of the results. The results and recommendations for action will be documented in a final report.

4 Work plan

4.1 WP 1: Inception report

Goal of the WP: The aim of the concept phase is to develop a joint understanding of the evaluation with the client and to refine and align the impact model and the evaluation design accordingly in this inception report. Due to the overall time frame of the study, this WP serves to thoroughly plan and effectively prepare further data collection steps such as drafting and finalising the survey questionnaires and interview guides.

Procedure:

With the submission of the Inception Report, we have **already completed** the following steps:

- Kick Off discussion with the Base4NFDI team on the 18th December to discuss the impact model of the evaluation and to develop a common and deeper understanding of the background and context of the evaluation
- A comprehensive document analysis (e.g. Base4NFDI project proposal, consortia feedback on basic service proposals, "survey of the Base4NFDI accompanying research", protocols of the consortia assembly and further material published on the Base4NFDI Zenodo community)
- 3 scoping interviews with the NFDI directorate, a member of the Scientific Council/IAB and a SER
- Submission of a draft survey questionnaire on 23rd January
- Discussion of the evaluation concept and the online survey design with TA4 on 27th January.

Table 2 shows the **remaining steps of the inception phase** which includes contacting interview partners for the first interview programme in early February, finalising the survey questionnaires and pre-testing the survey.

Table 2 Inception phase: timeline of remaining steps

Date	Step
03.-06.02.25	Interview initiation: contacting interview partners (interview phase 1)
04.02.25	Technopolis receives comments/feedback on survey questionnaires
07.02.25	Technopolis receives comments/feedback on inception report
10.02.25	Final scoping interview
14.02.25	Submission: Final inception report and survey questionnaires
17.-21.02.25	Technical implementation of the survey
24.-28.02.25	Survey pre-testing + start of interview programme
03.-06.03.25	Start survey (Duration until end of March)

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4.2 WP 2: Interview programme 1

Goal: The interview programme 1 aims at capturing both the internal and external perspectives regarding the effectiveness, efficiency, coherence and relevance of the project. Overall, we plan to conduct approx. 35 interviews. The list of interviewees can be found in Appendix B.

Contents and procedure: Table 3 displays all actors we plan to speak with and which thematic areas we want to cover for the interviews based on the role(s) of the interviewee. Interviewees involved in multiple contexts within the project are asked about all relevant topics that align with their diverse perspectives. Overall, the interviews cover the following five key topics, with a particular focus on collaboration between different actors, satisfaction with specific aspects of the project, potential areas for optimisation, and identifying what is working well (see Appendix A for the interview guide):

- Internal structures of Base4NFDI
- The identification and proposal process for basic services
- The development process for basic service
- Decision procedures
- Relevance for the NFDI community
- Strategic aspects / governance of Base4NFDI

We plan to interview two members of each task area, thereby covering both the perspective of a spokesperson as well as the team member perspective. The team member perspective of TA3 is covered by the planned interview with a SLO. Additionally, to the scoping interview with a SER, we conduct a group interview with several other SERs. The main topic for interviews with **Base4NFDI members** will be **internal structures** of the project since we expect to get key insights on this level of the evaluation (level 1) primarily from interviews with Base4NFDI, while interviews and online surveys with other actors can only rather complement these findings from an outsider's perspective on selected aspects. TA 3 (including SLO) is especially relevant for the identification and proposal process and TA 1 and TA2 additionally for the development process. Interviews with TA4 also cover aspects regarding decision procedures, relevance and governance/strategy. We anticipate that the group interview with SER will provide valuable

insights into the relevance for the consortia, in addition to shedding light on the development process. The interviews with PIs from developer teams will address a wide range of aspects, including the identification and development of basic services, decision-making processes, and relevance. TEC interviews will primarily focus on decision-making, relevance, and strategy. Interviews with section and consortia speakers will cover topics such as service identification, decision-making processes, relevance, and strategy. Members from strategic governance bodies (e.g. Scientific Senate and IAB) will naturally focus on governance and strategy, while also providing insights into relevance.

Table 3 Interview topics covered per target group

Actor (no. of interviews)	Internal structures	Identification and proposal process	Development process	Decision procedures	Relevance	Governance/Strategy
TA1 (2)						
TA2 (2)						
TA3 / SLO (1+1)						
TA4 (2)						
SER (1 + group interview)						
TEC (3)						
Developer teams (6)						
Section speaker (4)						
Consortia speaker (4)						
Strategy (3 +2+2)						

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A semi-structured interview guideline (see Appendix A) serves as the foundation for the interviews, providing both structure and flexibility for individual additions. To minimize the effort required from interviewees, the interviews are conducted online (e.g., via Teams, or if preferred via Zoom or Webex). Interviewees are initially contacted via email and provided with the guiding questions in advance. All interviews are thoroughly documented through detailed protocols. Participants can choose to conduct the interview in either English or German. For the analysis, we utilise the software Atlas.ti, which supports qualitative coding and enables a nuanced and detailed examination of all perspectives. This approach also allows for semi-quantification of certain viewpoints, such as identifying majority, minority, and individual opinions. All information gathered during the interviews will be treated confidentially. Direct quotes will be avoided in the final report to ensure the anonymity of the interviewees.

4.3 WP 3: Online surveys

The qualitative results from WP 2 on the internal and external perspective are going to be contrasted by two online surveys with 1) members of the consortia (stakeholder perspective of the NFDI community) and 2) the developer teams (project member perspective)

Aim of the WP: We consider both only surveys as an essential instrument to capture a broad range of opinions and quantitatively examine internal and external perspectives on Base4NFDI,

especially regarding the relevance of the project (consortia survey) and the development process (developer teams survey)

Contents and procedure: The survey questionnaires for the survey can be found in Appendix C and has already been distributed with the client. We aim to keep the effort and time required for the survey as low as possible and to avoid a repetitive survey. The online surveys will be designed, implemented and extensively pre-tested with the client during the inception phase (for the timeline see WP 1). Both surveys will be sent out to the participants in early March and last until end of March. The online surveys are implemented in accordance with GDPR requirements using the survey software of Limesurvey. As the working language throughout the project is English, the surveys will be conducted exclusively in English, contrary to what was originally planned in the proposal. However, for open-ended responses, we will explicitly state that answers can be provided in either German or English to allow German native speakers to respond with greater nuance.

4.3.1 *Survey with consortia members*

Since no complete and comprehensive contact information about consortia members is available to the evaluation team, the survey will be distributed using a “snowball” system. Therefore, we will contact each consortia coordinator directly via mail and ask them to share the survey with their consortia members (see Appendix D for the list of consortia coordinators). We aim for wide dispersion of the survey but must rely on consortia coordinators for distributing the survey. Therefore, each consortia receives an individual access token attached to the survey URL which allows us to track if the survey has been disseminated in each consortium. Thereby, we can contact specific consortia coordinators directly and ask them again to share the link in their consortium. In addition, we plan to ask the coordinators to send at least one reminder about halfway through the survey (e.g. 2 weeks after survey start).

Since many questions are aimed at obtaining individual opinions and assessments, the unit of analysis are individuals which are active in the consortia and not in their role as institutional employees. The heterogeneity of respondents in the survey is another challenge as the degrees of involvement in Base4NFDI likely vary significantly among them. We assume that the consortia coordinators are best placed to determine which members of their consortia are most suitable to complete the survey. Therefore, the respondents will receive a cover letter where we inform them 1) about the goals and the objectives of the evaluation, 2) the contents of the survey and 3) the target groups of the survey. Moreover, we will also ask them to send the survey to a minimum number of respondents and to ensure that the institutions of the consortia are represented in a balanced way in the selection to ensure a representative sample of the consortium. Suitable respondents can and should come from all target groups of the consortia, including applicant institutions, co-applicant institutions, participants, and supporters. However, a minimum level of knowledge about the project is required to complete the survey meaningfully—specifically, a basic understanding that basic services for the NFDI community are being developed that can be used by potentially all consortia. As some people are members of different consortia, the invitation text will explicitly state which consortium this invitation refers to. Furthermore, we plan to use filter questions to guide respondents through the survey, ensuring that they are only presented with questions relevant to their project knowledge (e.g. about proposal process or decision procedures). This approach will also help keep the survey duration as short as possible for respondents. We estimate a completion time of approximately 10 to 20 minutes, depending on their level of involvement in the project. Moreover, we offer respondents with a particularly high willingness to answer the opportunity to elaborate on the answers in more detail in open questions for each thematic area and offer them the opportunity to provide us their contact data which would allow us to invite them to the interview programme 2.

In order to prevent individuals from manipulating this open survey, we can, for example, track the IP address of the respondents in anonymised form and monitor the response time for the survey. This would help identify "fast-clickers" who complete the survey in an unusually short time.

After completion of the survey, the collected data will be evaluated both quantitatively and qualitatively (text analysis of the free-field answers). Here, essential terms could be processed in a visually appealing way, e.g. with WordClouds. Moreover, our approach also allows for disaggregated analyses by groups (e.g. by scientific field, type of institution, degree of involvement in Base4NFDI decision-making processes etc.).

4.3.2 Survey with the developer teams

In contrast to the survey with consortia members, the survey with the developer teams will be a closed survey where all members of the developer teams of basic services will receive an individual access token to answer the survey questions. We plan to invite all developer teams to the survey that have been accepted in the first six proposal rounds (6th round in August 2024) who have already been to start their work until now (IAM4NFDI, TS4NFDI, PID4NFDI, KGI4NFDI, DMP4NFDI, Jupyter4NFDI, nfdi.software and RDMTraining4NFDI) resulting in around 100 possible respondents for the survey.

The respondents will be contacted directly by Technopolis and will be informed about the goals of the evaluation and this survey. Reminders will be sent after 7 and 14 days to the respondents which have yet not answered the survey.

Disaggregated analyses by group (e.g. developer teams, current development stage) are possible if the number of respondents is sufficiently high, and anonymity can be guaranteed.

4.4 WP 4: Interview deep-dives & focus groups

Goal: The goal of this work package is to contextualise critical findings of the previous data collection steps as well as to identify reasons and solution strategies to these findings. New insights gained from this data collection step are going to be synthesized with previous findings to integrate new perspectives and deepen existing findings.

Procedure:

First, the findings of interview programme 1 and both surveys will be compared in various ways, e.g.:

- Results from the developer team survey vs. the consortia team survey
- Disaggregated analysis of the consortia member survey (see above for details)
- Disaggregated analysis of the developer teams survey (see above for details)
- Interview results from different perspectives, e.g.:
 - Views from TA members on internal structure
 - Views from developer teams and consortia/sections on identification and submission process
 - Perspectives on the development process from TAs and developer teams

Opinions on decision procedures from the TEC, sections/consortia, developer teams and TA4

- Assessments on the relevance of developed services from consortia speaker, developer teams and from strategic governance bodies
- General views on the strategic governance from different stakeholders and actors

Moreover, we will also compare the general and stakeholder-specific qualitative answers with both the quantitative answers from the survey as well as qualitative, open answers from the survey on each thematic area. This enables us to compare the individual perspectives of highly involved actors with a broader spectrum of viewpoints and opinions, while also incorporating quantifiable data on project satisfaction.

We expect to select about 3-5 topics that need deeper investigation which could range from the certain elements of the internal structure of the project, specific collaboration between different stakeholders, certain elements during the identification, development and decision-making process or the expected sustainability of the project or strategical aspects.

Overall, we plan to conduct around 15 further interviews and 2 focus groups. The exact number of interviews and focus groups is to be determined in accordance with the client and given the results of the previous data collection steps. Interviews offer the advantage of in-depth, individual insights, allowing for a more detailed exploration of personal experiences, while focus groups provide the benefit of diverse perspectives through group interaction, fostering dynamic discussions and the identification of shared viewpoints. Possible interviewees for the deep dives will be identified through the consortia survey and through available contact lists (e.g. developer teams, consortia spokespersons etc.). The topics and the selection of interviewees will be discussed in accordance with the client. Interview results will again be coded using Atlas.ti.

4.5 WP 5: Workshops with Base4NFDI members

Goal: The goal is to conduct two workshops with the Base4NFDI core team to present, discuss and validate the evaluation results. Both workshops will focus on assessing the overall impact, alignment, and optimisation potential of Base4NFDI.

Procedure:

We envision two workshops:

- Workshop 1 with members from TA 1 and TA 2 and selected Service Stewards
- Workshop 2 with members from TA 3 and TA 4 and selected Service Stewards

Both workshops will cover all three levels of the evaluation since they are closely intertwined. While Workshop 1 focuses slightly more on level 2 (service development), Workshop 2 focuses slightly more on level 3 (relevance and strategy) of the evaluation.

The workshops will have an approximate duration of two hours. It will begin with a **presentation of relevant preliminary evaluation results**, providing an overview of key findings. This will include insights drawn from surveys and Interview Programme 1, as well as preliminary observations from in-depth analyses of specific areas. Following this, the **results will be validated** in collaboration with the Base4NFDI team to ensure accuracy and relevance. The session will conclude with a **structured discussion** aimed at developing suggestions for **improvements and optimisation** of the project, integrating diverse perspectives to support its further development. A schedule for the workshops could therefore be as follows:

- Welcome, recap on the objectives of the evaluation (10 min)
- Presentation of relevant preliminary evaluation results (30 min)
- Discussion and validation of results (40 min)
- Developing suggestions for improvements and optimisation (35 min)
- Conclusion and next steps (5 min)

To prepare for the workshops, we conduct an internal workshop to discuss and compare the results of the evaluation and to formulate discussion points. The workshops are set to take place

virtually in order to keep the workload for the participants as low as possible. The workshops can be accompanied in a structured way by using a PowerPoint presentation and virtual whiteboards (e.g. MIRO). Jan Biela and Lennart Stoy are scheduled to moderate the workshops.

The final selection of the participants is made in consultation with the client and can be extended. We plan to invite all members of TA1 and TA2 together with selected Service Stewards for workshop 1 and all members of TA3 and TA4 and selected Service Stewards for workshop 2. In the selection process, we ensured that both the roles of participants within the project and the diversity of their home institutions were taken into account, while also including individuals who had not been part of the original interview programme.

After contacting the participants via email, the appointment will be efficiently scheduled using Doodle. Prior to the workshop, participants will receive a concise summary of the evaluation, including key findings and the agenda. The outcomes of the focus group workshop will be incorporated into the data triangulation process and the evaluation report, forming the foundation for the recommendations for action. Additionally, the perspectives shared by participants will contribute to validating previous findings and provide valuable insights for shaping the project's future direction and implementation.

4.6 WP 6: Data triangulation and evaluation report

Aim of the WP: The results of the evaluation will be written down in a final report which has to be approved by the client. The most important results are also consolidated in an executive summary (approx. 5 pages).

Procedure: The final report summarises the subject of the evaluation, the evaluation concept and methodological approach, compiles the empirical results of the evaluation and brings them together in a synthesis in order to gain central findings.

The evaluation is guided by questions categorised according to the DAC/OECD criteria—relevance, effectiveness, efficiency, and coherence—across the three levels of evaluation (see Table 1). These questions form the basis for a systematic assessment and structured reporting.

In the initial phase, the collected data will be systematically linked to the evaluation questions and analysed to formulate well-founded responses. To assess relevance, the evaluation examines whether the funded projects are widely regarded by consortia as useful and supportive in achieving their respective objectives. To assess the effectiveness, we examine whether NFDI structures are sufficiently involved. Efficiency is evaluated by determining whether decision-making processes for the (further) development of services are perceived as transparent and comprehensible by the consortia and whether the TAs consider the organisational structure to be efficient and appropriate in fulfilling their responsibilities. For coherence, the assessment examines whether the technical expertises represented in the TEC are well aligned from a stakeholder perspective and how the development process is perceived overall.

Particular attention is given to findings across different evaluation levels and perspectives (Base4NFDI core team, project teams, and external stakeholders), ensuring a comprehensive analysis of processes from multiple viewpoints. This methodological approach allows for the targeted identification of success factors and challenges, which are then synthesised and presented in the report. Based on these insights, recommendations for the project's further development are formulated.

A preliminary structure of the report can be found here below. Overall, we expect the report to have a length of around 40-50 pages.

1. Introduction (ca. 2 pages)
2. Context and goals of the evaluation (ca. 5 pages)
 - i) Impact model
 - ii) Goals of the evaluation
 - iii) Concept and methodology
3. Empirical results & evaluation (30-40 pages)
 - i) Internal structure of Base4NFDI
 - ii) Process for service development
 - a. Identification of basic services candidates
 - b. Voting and decision-making processes
 - c. Development and deployment
 - iii) Relevance for Base4NFDI & strategic alignment
4. Conclusion & Recommendations for action (ca. 3 pages)
5. Appendix (e.g. interview guides, survey questionnaires, further charts from the survey)

The first draft of both the final report and executive summary will be made available to the client by **mid-July 2025**. These documents will then be presented and discussed in a final workshop. Following this, the reports will be finalised, proofread, and submitted. The client will formally accept the final report and executive summary by **mid-August**, at which point they will be provided in electronic format and, upon request, as a bound print version. Both documents will be written in **English**.

5 Time plan

The total **time frame** of the evaluation is about 7.5 months and will be completed by mid-August 2025. The following figure shows when which work packages and steps are planned. A thorough preparation of the work packages is necessary to ensure efficient and high-quality implementation of the WP.

The work plan for the inception phase has already been outlined above. We plan to start the interview phase of WP2 in late February and to run the surveys (WP 3) in March. WPs 2 and 3 are expected to be largely completed at the beginning of April, so that the identification of the aspects to be considered in depth in WP 4 and the initiation of the associated interviews and focus groups can begin before Easter holidays. If some topics emerge early on as suitable for a deep dive, we can also start initiating some interviews as early as mid-March. This process step is carried out in close coordination with the client and is based on the results of the surveys and interviews.

The in-depth interviews and focus groups are to be conducted from the second half of April to mid-May. The survey phase for WP 4 is thus just as long as the survey phase for WP 2, although significantly fewer interviews must be conducted. The final workshops in WP 5 will take place in the second half of May. The workshops will be designed in parallel with the completion of WP 4 and refined based on the interim results from WP 4. Data triangulation and reporting will start in June. A first draft report will be sent to the client in mid-July. The final report will be presented at a meeting of the Base4NFDI Management Committee in mid-August.

Figure 4 Time plan for the evaluation

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Appendix A Interview guide

Table 4 Interview guide: question blocks

Level	Questions	Actors/stakeholders
Internal structure and responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How would you describe the area of responsibility of your task area? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do you have a particular role within your task area? How are the roles distributed in your task area? - Within your task area: have you made any changes to how you complete your tasks or fulfil/define your roles compared to how it was originally intended in the project proposal of Base4NFDI? If yes, why? • Do you feel you have access to all the necessary resources and information to perform your role effectively? If not, what additional support would be helpful? • Are there any tasks or objectives in Base4NFDI that are in your opinion not yet adequately addressed? (e.g. due to lack of financial or personnel resources) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overall <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In your task area • Are there mechanisms to refine the internal structure of Base4NFDI and its processes? (e.g. feedback mechanisms) • Who are you in frequent contact with? (e.g. consortia, certain members of consortia, sections/working groups, developer teams, TEC, consortia spokesperson)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What topics are you discussing frequently with these actors/stakeholders? - Do you find that you can help these external stakeholders/actors directly with their queries/concerns or can you refer them to a suitable contact point at Base4NFDI? - satisfaction question intra TA? • To what extent are you collaborating with other task areas (or SERs) to fulfil your tasks? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What topics are you discussing frequently with other task areas? - Do you feel that roles and responsibilities between task areas are clearly defined and communicated? - Are you satisfied overall with how the task areas are collaborating? Is the collaboration constructive in your opinion? - How would you describe the internal communication and workflow within Base4NFDI? Are there particular strengths or areas for improvement? - In your opinion, how well do the roles and tasks overall match the project's needs? (e.g. is any role or task missing? Are there any overlaps? • To what extent do strategic governance bodies (e.g. International Advisory Board, Scientific Senate) shape the project's overall structure and decision-making framework? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How is the project structure of Base4NFDI embedded in international structures such as EOSC or the Research Data Alliance? • To what extent are strategic governance bodies involved in the operative work of the project? What mechanisms support their integration? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How is the International Advisory Board involved in the processes of Base4NFDI? - How is the Scientific Senate and other actors from the NFDI involved in (decision-making) processes of Base4NFDI? 	TAs (with SERs)

<p>Process for discussing and identifying basic service candidates in the sections</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Have you been involved in discussions about proposing a basic service (e.g. in the sections, in a consortium etc.)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If so, which service(s) were the discussions about? - In your view, what criteria should be used to identify needs for basic services? (e.g. relevance for all/most/many consortia, sustainability of service solutions, easy/fast to implement) - In your opinion, do the discussions in the sections and working groups reflect the needs in your consortium? ● Do you know how ideas for submitting basic service proposals are generally discussed in the sections/working groups? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To your knowledge, what relevant processes and mechanisms are in place for this? (e.g. informal discussions, regularly meetings) - Who is involved in the discussions and the decision-making processes? - How are decisions on proposing a basic service taken? (e.g. is there a voting process? If yes, please describe how it is organised.) ● How different voices and opinions are heard and reflected in the debates? <p>Are there larger "interest groups" within the sections which usually have the same perspective, or do the groups differ strongly from decision to decision?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Are you satisfied overall with how these processes are organised? ● Do you know how the teams that come together for a basic service proposal are initiated? (e.g. discussions in a working group) What criteria are most relevant for deciding to submit a proposal? ● How does the Base4NFDI core team support the process for discussing and proposing basic services? <p>[Consortia/Sections only]: Do you know whom to contact at Base4NFDI if you have any queries about the proposal process?</p> <p>Are there any aspects where more support by Base4NFDI is needed in your opinion?</p> <p>Are there any aspects of the collaboration which can be improved?</p>	<p>TA 1 + 2 + 3 and SER, SLO</p> <p>Section speakers, Consortia speakers, Developer Teams</p>
<p>Decision making processes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How satisfied are you overall with the decision-making processes and structures for developing a basic service (e.g. voting in the TEC and in the consortia assembly, three steps for service development)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are you satisfied with how the decision-making structures are designed? (e.g. are they effective and efficient) ● Is the decision-making process flexible enough to account for the variety of basic services that are proposed? ● How satisfied are you overall with the decisions of the TEC? <p>Do you believe the composition of the TEC is well-balanced and adequately equipped to evaluate the technical aspects of the various proposed basic services effectively?</p> <p>Do you believe the decision-making processes in the consortia assembly are adequate to evaluate the basic services?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In your opinion, do you consider the decisions made in the TEC/consortia assembly to be transparent and fair? ● [TEC only]: How does the TEC evaluate proposals for basic service candidates for each development phase? What criteria are most relevant? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initialisation phase: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Assessment of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the basic service ○ Concept for implementation ○ Support of consortia ○ Need for technical development in NFDI 	<p>Developer teams, TEC</p> <p>Consortia spokesperson</p> <p>Section spokesperson</p> <p>TA4</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Quality and maturity ◦ Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Risks (SWOT) ◦ Work plan, project organization ◦ Deliverables and milestones ◦ Overall assessment/justification – Integration phase: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Assessment of the TRL of the basic service ◦ Evaluation of the initialisation phase ◦ Support of consortia ◦ Financial calculations ◦ Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Risks (SWOT) ◦ Work plan and project organization ◦ Integration into the (inter)national landscape (particular EOSC) ◦ Deliverables, milestones, and KPIs ◦ Interoperability with existing solutions in consortia / NFDI services ◦ Overall assessment/justification – Ramping-Up: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Support of consortia ◦ sustainability of service solution ◦ Assessment of the TRL of the basic service ◦ Final TRL ● What trade-offs do you have to make when evaluating the basic services? ● In your opinion, are the criteria sufficient to make sure that the developed basic services are state-of-the art? ● Are there also any strategic criteria for evaluating the basic services? (e.g. relevance for infrastructure institutions that may provide the service) ● What role do the needs and concerns of different consortia play in the decisions? ● Do you have sufficient resources to fulfil your tasks in the TEC? (e.g. enough time and support) ● [TA4] To what extent do you provide feedback on the service proposals submitted? ● [Consortia spokespersons]: What are the most relevant criteria in the consortia assembly for evaluating basic services? Do you consider these criteria adequate? ● How is it ensured that the proposed basic services meet the needs of the consortia? (e.g. being state-of-the-art, being interoperable with existing solutions) ● How is it ensured that the developed services are sustainable after development? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To what extent have consortia and institutions need to commit to develop a basic service? ● [For TEC/consortia spokespersons only] How does the Base4NFDI team support you with fulfilling your tasks in the TEC/consortia assembly? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Is there any support missing? ● [Non-Base4NFDI] Do you know who to contact within Base4NFDI if you have questions/concerns about the decision-making process? ● Are there any improvements to the decision-making processes of Base4NFDI you can think of? 	
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<p>Development / Implementation of basic services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● [Developer teams]: Can you describe the current state of your project? ● Are you satisfied overall with the structures, processes and support that Base4NFDI creates for the developer teams? <p>In your opinion, are the financial and personnel resources sufficient to develop basic services?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Are they flexible enough? <p>Is the development process flexible enough to account for specific requirements of different services?</p> <p>Is the process for developing a basic service fast enough to deliver quick results while ensuring high-quality solutions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● [Developer teams] How does Base4NFDI support you in the development process? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is there any support missing? ● To what extent are consortia involved in the process? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent is their feedback taken into account? - To what extent is their feedback? Do they commit to deploy the basic services? ● What activities and types of support exist/are planned to promote the basic services in the consortia? (e.g. active learning activities of consortia in e.g. trainings/workshops or passive learning activities in e.g. roadshows/presentations) ● Are there any improvements to the process of service development you can think of? 	<p>Developer teams, SER TA 1 + 2</p>
<p>Relevance for NFDI Community</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● [Consortia]: Which of the developed services do you consider useful for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Base4NFDI overall - For your consortium - Your institution ● In terms of potential user groups of the service (e.g. institutions, consortia), what criteria must a developed service meet in your opinion to be considered a success? ● Do the developed basic services reflect and meet the needs and objectives of your consortia? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In your opinion, how well do the services offered by Base4NFDI align with the current and future needs of your consortia? - How well do they align with the strategic goals of your consortia? ● [Consortia only] Do you plan to replace existing services in your consortia/institution with basic services? ● [Consortia only] Do you receive sufficient support from Base4NFDI and the developer teams for deploying the services in your consortia? ● What improvements or additional support do you believe Base4NFDI could offer to make their services more relevant to the consortia's work? ● When you look at all services that have been granted funding by Base4NFDI, are there any gaps, i.e. basic services that would be needed, but are not being developed? 	<p>Developer teams, TA 3, TA 4 SER TEC Consortia spokesperson Section spokesperson Strategy</p>
<p>Overall steering and strategy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Which Base4NFDI strategy processes are you involved in? ● Are you in dialogue with other NFDI stakeholders about the project? If yes, about which aspects? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From consortia - NFDI actors (e.g. Scientific Senate) - International actors (e.g. EOOSC, RDA) 	<p>Strategy TA 4 TEC Consortia spokesperson Section spokesperson</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In your opinion, are all relevant stakeholders adequately involved in the project? • Do you think that Base4NFDI will advance / support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the development of structures and bodies of the NFDI? - the German research data infrastructure landscape in general? - Data infrastructure user groups in the NFDI community and beyond - the international research data infrastructure landscape (e.g. EOSC, RDA)? • In your opinion, Is the project structure of Base4NFDI (as a joint initiative of all consortia) overall adequate to meet its goals? • Are there any improvements to Base4NFDI you can think of? 	
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Appendix B Survey questionnaires

Available as pdf files in separate documents.

